

INFORMATION ABOUT THE ORIGINS AND HISTORY OF ART THERAPY

Turemuratova Aziza Begibaevna

Assistant, Department of Pedagogy and Psychology, Karakalpak State University named after Berdakh, Republic of Karakalpakstan.

Azizaturemuratova85@gmail.com

Tajibaeva Shaxnozabanu Qirg'izbay qizi

Student of Karakalpak State University.

Qonisbaeva Gulzada Botabek qizi

Student of Karakalpak State University.

Menglibaeva Gulayim Baxadir qizi

Student of Karakalpak State University.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15256725>

Abstract. *In this study, we have provided information about the origins, stages of development, and history of art therapy. We have also provided information about the advantages of using psychotherapeutic methods through psychological approaches.*

Keywords: *Psychological research, art therapy, psychotherapist, Psychological approaches, psychic activity.*

ART TERAPIYANI KELIB CHIQISHI VA TARIXI HAQIDA MA'LUMOTLAR

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu tadqiqotda art terapiyani kelib chiqishi, rivojlanish bosqichlari va tarixi haqidagi ma'lumotlarni keltirib o'tganmiz. Shuningdek, psixologik yondashuvlar orqali psixoterapevtik usullardan foydalanishning afzal taraflari haqida ma'lumotlar berib o'tilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Psixologik tadqiqotlar, art terapiya, psixoterapevt, Psixologik yondashuvlar, psixik faoliyat.*

ИНФОРМАЦИЯ О ПРОИСХОЖДЕНИИ И ИСТОРИИ АРТ-ТЕРАПИИ

Аннотация. *В данном исследовании мы представили информацию о происхождении, этапах развития и истории арт-терапии. Также была предоставлена информация о преимуществах использования психотерапевтических методов с использованием психологических подходов.*

Ключевые слова: *Психологические исследования, арт-терапия, психотерапевт, психологические подходы, психическая деятельность.*

In the current era, the rapid and harmonious development of education and culture, the improvement of social relations and political order, the further development of the human being,

who is the main productive force and the highest wealth of society, requires a new, more extensive approach to the education and upbringing of the younger generation. The task of psychology is to teach students to organize the essence of events and phenomena in reality and society, general psychological phenomena, situations and processes in the life of society, to analyze the development of the individual and the factors affecting it, his individual psychological characteristics, emotional and volitional qualities. The fact that more than 300 branches of psychology are currently developing as a science indicates that it is becoming more and more consolidated in the system of sciences. General psychology is a special field that studies the general laws of mental activity and their specific aspects. Psychology of youth studies the process of mental development of people of different ages from birth to the end of their lives, the laws of the formation and interaction of the personality, the principles of change specific to the age of the individual. Psychology, as a holistic and independent science, serves the formation of mentality in people, and its relevance to the human factor requires its direct connection with all sciences that study problems in this direction in a certain sense. These are, first of all, the fields of social and humanitarian sciences, and psychology has a unique position among them. One of the new areas of psychology is art therapy. Art therapy is often mentioned in modern psychology. The types and methods of this technique are diverse, which provides a huge scope for experiments. It literally means art therapy. Indeed, during the sessions, patients have the opportunity to express their feelings and emotions, explore their individuality using various forms of art, including painting, dance, composition, sculpture, etc. Before considering the most popular types of art therapy in psychology, it is worth paying attention to the history of the creation and development of this correctional method. Initially, the scheme of art therapy was presented in the theories of such famous figures as Z. Freud, C. Jung, A. Maslow. However, in practice, hypothetical models began to be used only in the 30s of the 20th century. A similar correctional method began to be used in the treatment of children who emigrated from the USA to Germany after the end of the war. At that time, art therapy was the only way to cope with stress and combat the traumas received during their stay in Nazi camps. The first experiments gave positive results, so "art therapy" became increasingly popular. Today, almost all types of art therapy are widely used in psychotherapy. This method allows a person to cope with and solve many of his problems, to discover new facets of his personality. The term "art therapy" ("art" - art, "art therapy" - art therapy) means the treatment of plastic visual arts to express their psycho-emotional state. This term was first used by A. Hill in 1938, describing work with patients suffering from tuberculosis in sanatoriums. Art therapy appeared in the 30s of the 20th century.

Art therapy methods were first used in the United States in working with children brought from Nazi concentration camps. At the beginning of its development, art therapy reflected the psychoanalytic views of Z. Freud. According to Jung, the final product of the client's artistic activity (be it painting, sculpture, installation) expresses his unconscious mental processes. In 1960, the Art Therapy Association was founded in America. Numerous and often contradictory definitions of art therapy - or art psychotherapy - have been put forward since the term was coined, and the profession first emerged in the late 1940s. In Great Britain, artist Adrian Hill is credited with being the first person to use the term "art therapy" to describe the therapeutic use of painting.

For Hill, who discovered the therapeutic benefits of drawing and painting while recovering from tuberculosis, the value of art therapy was in "the full engagement of the mind (as well as the fingers) and the frequent release of its creative energy" (Hill, 1948: 101–02). This, Hill said, allowed the patient to "build up a strong defense against his misfortunes." Around the same time, Margaret Naumberg also began to use the term art therapy to describe her work in the United States. Naumberg's art therapy model is based on his own methods. The liberation of the unconscious through spontaneous artistic expression; its roots are in the transference relationship between patient and therapist and the encouragement of free communication. It is closely related to psychoanalytic theory. Treatment depends on the development of the transference relationship and the constant effort to obtain the patient's own interpretation of the symbolic designs. The images created are a form of communication between patient and therapist, which constitute symbolic discourse. Although the approaches to art therapy adopted by Hill and Naumberg were very different and have been replaced by subsequent developments. Within the art therapy profession, their work has nevertheless had a significant and lasting influence. This is because art therapy in the UK has developed along "two parallel lines" (Waller, 1993: 8). The therapy promoted by Hill and the use of art in therapy, championed by Naumberg as a The first of these approaches emphasizes the healing potential inherent in the process of making art, while the second emphasizes the importance of the therapeutic relationship established between the art therapist, the client, and the artwork. As the art therapy profession has emerged, definitions have become more nuanced. In contemporary terms, art therapy should be defined as a form of therapy in which the creation of images and objects plays a central role in the psychotherapeutic relationship established between the art therapist and the client. Clients referred to an art therapist do not need to have prior experience or skill in the arts, and the art therapist is not primarily concerned with aesthetic or diagnostic assessment of the client's image.

The overall goal of practitioners is to enable the client to achieve personal change and growth through the use of art materials in a safe and supportive environment. Art therapy is the therapeutic use of art making within a professional relationship by people who have experienced illness, trauma, or life challenges, and by people seeking personal development. By creating art and reflecting on the products and processes of art, people can increase their awareness of themselves and others in coping with symptoms, stress, and traumatic experiences; develop cognitive skills; and enjoy the life-affirming pleasures of art making. Art therapy uses the creative process of creating art and reflecting on clients to enhance and improve the mental, physical, and emotional well-being of individuals. While these collective, formally approved definitions help to clarify what art therapy is, the following examples show that individual art therapists often have their own. It is difficult to briefly define art therapy. For some, it is about the art itself as the primary agent of the therapeutic experience. For others, the relationship with the therapist is the crucial element. I like to think that both have their place and that neither is better or more important than the other. I think it depends on the client and how they work. It is important to note here that in art therapy, this relationship focuses on the visual arts (primarily painting, drawing, and sculpture) and does not typically involve the use of other art forms such as music, drama, or dance.

The goals of art therapy vary depending on the specific needs of the individuals with whom the art therapist works, and these needs may change as the therapeutic relationship develops. For one person, the art therapy process may encourage the art therapist to share and explore emotional distress through the creation and discussion of images, while for another client it may focus on providing them with an opportunity to engage in their own activities. colored pencils and markers, thereby developing new ways of giving form to previously unexpressed feelings. Although it is often assumed that this is the case, individuals who only have a technical background in the visual arts are not likely to benefit from art therapy. The ability - for example, when art is used primarily for recreational or educational purposes - may only serve to mask what art therapy is most concerned with. That is, through the symbolic expression of emotion and human experience through the medium of art. Art therapy can help people with a variety of needs and difficulties for a variety of reasons. Creating images in the context of a supportive relationship, thinking and feeling in images, including the use of imagination and taking risks, contributes to a person's emotional growth, self-esteem, psychological and social integration. In working with children, art therapy mainly uses such areas as sand therapy, fairy tale therapy, isotherapy (painting therapy, fine arts). Elements of these methods are often used in their work by kindergarten teachers and psychologists, teachers of developmental centers, speech therapists and correctional teachers.

Art therapy also works great with children with developmental disabilities. Art therapy is called "soft" because in this case the degree of influence of the psychotherapist on the client's personality is minimized, and the treatment process itself is more like a hobby. At the same time, the value and benefits of such therapy should not be underestimated. Creativity is when a person projects their inner experiences into their creations. Such projection is not done: emotions, thoughts, experiences, and memories bypass the conscious mind and go outside, and therefore are unable to correct or criticize the mind.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be said that art therapy is a method of symbolically expressing the content of a person's inner world through painting, modeling, dance and other forms of art and creativity, and as a result achieving inner harmony and psychological well-being. Therefore, art therapy methods are classified as projective methods of psychodiagnostics.

REFERENCES

1. Turemuratova, Aziza, Rita Kurbanova, and Barno Saidboyeva. "EDUCATIONAL TRADITIONS IN SHAPING THE WORLDVIEW OF YOUNG PEOPLE IN FOLK PEDAGOGY." *Modern Science and Research* 2.10 (2023): 318-322.
2. Turemuratova, Aziza, and Kamola Yoldasheva. "PSYCHOLOGICAL CONFIDENTIALITY OF THE FORMATION OF STUDENTS' COLLABORATIVE SKILLS BASED ON MULTI-VECTOR APPROACHES IN EDUCATION." *Modern Science and Research* 4.4 (2025): 262-269.
3. Turemuratova, Aziza, Shahlo Matmuratova, and Nargisa Tajieva. "THE DEPENDENCE OF MULTI-VECTOR APPROACHES ON PEDAGOGICAL METHODS AND PSYCHOLOGICAL TRAINING IN IMPROVING STUDENTS' COLLABORATIVE SKILLS BASED ON THE EDUCATIONAL PROGRAM." *Modern Science and Research* 4.4 (2025): 50-55.
4. Turemuratova, Aziza, and Marhabo Kenjayeva. "KO'P VEKTORLI YONDASHUVLAR ASOSIDA TALABALARNING KOLLABORATIV KO'NIKMALARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING PSIXOLOGIK TRENING USLUBI." *Modern Science and Research* 4.4 (2025): 252-261.
5. Turemuratova, Aziza, Umida Uzakbaeva, and Dilafro'z Nuriyeva. "BASIC CONCEPTS OF FAMILY PSYCHOLOGY AND OVERCOMING PSYCHOLOGICAL PROBLEMS." *Modern Science and Research* 4.4 (2025): 104-109.

6. Begibaevna, Turemuratova Aziza. "RESEARCH ON IMPROVING STUDENTS'COLLABORATIVE SKILLS BASED ON MULTI-VECTOR PSYCHOLOGICAL TRAINING APPROACHES."
7. Begibaevna, Turemuratova Aziza, Kushbaeva Indira Tursinbaevna, and Dawletmuratova Raxila Genjemuratovna. "THE MAIN ESSENCE OF DEVELOPING STUDENTS'COLLABORATIVE SKILLS BASED ON MULTI-VECTOR PEDAGOGICAL APPROACHES IN MODERN EDUCATION."
8. Jarilkapovich, Matjanov Aman. "Program Technology for Choosing an Effective Educational Methodology Based on Modern Pedagogical Research in The Educational System." *CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PEDAGOGICS* 6.02 (2025): 30-33.
9. Jarilkapovich, Matjanov Aman. "USE OF PEDAGOGICAL METHODS BASED ON THE MODERN EDUCATIONAL PROGRAM TO INCREASE THE EFFECTIVENESS OF EDUCATION." *European International Journal of Pedagogics* 4.06 (2024): 26-33.
10. Turemuratova, Aziza, Rita Kurbanova, and Barno Saidboyeva. "EDUCATIONAL TRADITIONS IN SHAPING THE WORLDVIEW OF YOUNG PEOPLE IN FOLK PEDAGOGY." *Modern Science and Research* 2.10 (2023): 318-322.
11. Kurbanova, R. J., and B. E. Saidboeva. "MAKTAB VA OILADA ESTETIK TARBIYANI SHAKLLANTIRISH JARAYONIDA O'QUVCHILARNING AKSIOLOGIK DUNYOQARASHINI RIVOJLANTIRISH." *Inter education & global study* 9 (2024): 114-121.
12. Jarasovna, Kurbanova Rita. "The Role of National Values in Shaping the Aesthetic Worldview of Schoolchildren." *International Journal of Pedagogics* 5.03 (2025): 55-58.
13. Asamatdinova, J., and B. Saidboeva. "Diagnosis and Correction of the Development of Value Orientation in Students in the Process of Moral and Aesthetic Education." *JournalNX* 9.6 (2023): 274-277.
14. Muratbayevna, Dauletova Gozal, and Madaminova Nargiza Qurbanbayevna. "BOLANING RIVOJLANISH DAVRI PSIXOLOGIYASI." *Scientific Impulse* 1 (2022): 33-35.
15. Jansulu, Tursinbaeva, and Mambetiyarova Venera. "SOTSIAL PSIXOLOGIYADA SHAXS MUAMMOSI." (2024).